

Local Stress Analysis of IGBTs Softly-Driven by Frequency Sweep in Induction Hobs

C. Ferrer, M. Fernández, M. Vellvehi, S. Llorente, X. Jordà, X. Perpiñà

Abstract — Die-level electrical stress caused by current crowding is investigated in Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) outside zero-voltage switching (ZVS) operation. This stress occurs during the turn-on phase of an induction cooking resonant inverter, where the switching frequency sweeps from 150 to 50 kHz. The stress is monitored on a sub-100 μ s timescale with a 10 μ m lateral resolution using an infrared (IR) thermographic setup. To improve signal-to-noise ratio and time resolution, a Fourier-based time reconstruction strategy is applied. Electrothermal SPICE simulations complement the interpretation of measurements, providing insights into current crowding under such stressful operating conditions. The analysis under soft-start conditions reveals two key findings. First, heat dissipation, and consequently current conduction, present a time-dependent two-dimensional distribution, with hotspots forming in low-impedance regions detectable via IR thermography. Second, in this non-homogeneous current distribution, the SPICE electrothermal model predicts the most frequently occurring value of the temperature distribution (statistical mode) across the active area more accurately than the mean value. This observation may establish a link to the concept of junction temperature, which is traditionally derived using thermo-sensitive electrical parameters.

Index Terms — Resonant converter, zero voltage switching, softly-driven, Fourier-based infrared thermography, Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor, hotspot.

I. INTRODUCTION

RESIDENTIAL building electrification with highly energy-efficient household appliances is one of the actions to shift to a more sustainable and greener economy. In this scenario, induction cooking has been and is still one of these technologies actively contributing to attaining these energy and climate goals [1], [2]. Thanks to advanced power conversion strategies, induction cooktops consume less energy than resistive-based electric cooktops and achieve higher heating efficiency [3], [4]. They also outperform other solutions in terms of safety, cleanliness, and heating speed [5], [6], enabling value-added functionalities that improve cooking flexibility.

Currently, half-bridge resonant inverters are the most popular topology in induction cooking, as they meet the key requirements for domestic use. They offer low cost [7], high efficiency (> 90%) [8], and reliable operation under limited-heat extraction conditions at medium switching frequencies (typically 30 – 75 kHz) [9], [10]. When this medium frequency current flows through an inductive load, it generates a magnetic field. This is achieved through two switching elements placed on the top (high) and bottom (low) sides of the half-bridge, which create a current path to

drive an equivalent load resulting from the cooking element and inductor interaction. Each switching element consists of a semiconductor transistor, a free-wheel diode, and a snubber capacitor (C_{snub}) connected in parallel. In this application, the most commonly used power semiconductor devices are the Silicon-based Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) and PIN diodes. IGBTs and PIN-diodes are preferred over other devices because of their lower cost, higher current conduction capability and suitability for the required power range.

Switching IGBTs at frequencies from a few tens to several hundred kHz is usual in resonant topologies. In other applications based on these converters, IGBTs are driven from 2.5 kHz [11] to 250 kHz [12], and can reach up to 3 MHz in Gallium Nitride-based systems [13]. To reduce turn-on losses ensuring their safe use, IGBTs are operated within the Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) condition. In this control strategy, the device is switched on when the collector-emitter voltage (V_{CE}) is close to 0 V. In induction cooktops, there are operating modes where ZVS condition can be lost temporarily. One of them is the soft-start and soft-stop modes. They consist in a switching frequency (f_{sw}) sweep, in a millisecond scale, from a high value down to the operation value near the RLC load resonance frequency (f_{res}) (soft-start), or vice versa (soft-stop).

From a die-level reliability perspective, the influence of ZVS conditions on current distribution within an IGBT during soft-start/stop driving is of concern, as it leads to local overstress due to higher power dissipation [14], [15]. Areas with current concentration due to current crowding effects form local hot spots [16], [17], [18]; where temperatures rise due to the higher turn-on losses induced by ZVS loss, making them the weakest points in the layout. To study this phenomenon and enable its mitigation through device layout, gate driving, or converter-level design, thermal imaging offers the most promising approach. By exploiting the Joule effect, hot spots under switching conditions can be studied non-invasively with adequate signal-to-noise ratio, time, and space resolution [16], [17]. Conventional temperature extraction methods, such as thermocouples and thermo-sensitive electrical parameters, are limited by packaging effects and electrical noise at high switching speeds, making accurate die-level monitoring difficult. Non-invasive thermal imaging offers improved spatial resolution and noise-free analysis, but limited frame rates and reduced thermal resolution from short integration times (t_{int}) pose challenges, requiring improvements in both thermal and time performance. Only one prior study has examined, in the frequency domain, this scenario for $f_{\text{sw}} < f_{\text{res}}$ using a reduced and non-representative f_{sw} value (9 kHz), yielding a stationary amplitude thermal map [16]. Consequently, no work addresses the real-operation case f_{sw}

Fig. 1. (a) Simplified half-bridge resonant inverter schematic, with a typical cooktop inductor pictured. Below, representative DUT turn-on waveforms inside ZVS (b) and outside ZVS (c).

$> f_{res}$ due to the lack of suitable processing methods in the time domain. Although heterodyne approach down converts high- f_{sw} thermal patterns into the camera bandwidth, heat diffusion blurs the thermal maps and, yields a stationary amplitude image [19], [20]. Thus, current crowding transients in real-operation regime ($f_{sw} > f_{res}$) have not been reported before.

To meet the time resolution requirements for accurate current crowding analysis, Fourier-series time reconstruction is a promising solution. This methodology has been recently introduced in thermal imaging for die-level functional inspection [21]. This approach enhances both the time resolution and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in image sequences. It is implemented with a periodic square amplitude modulation (SAM), which discretizes the power spectrum into the SAM's fundamental frequency and harmonics. The captured images undergo frequency-domain analysis for Fourier coefficients determination and subsequent time-domain reconstruction. This method has been successfully demonstrated in power devices with millisecond conduction times, longer than the tens of microseconds in real applications [21].

In this work, power semiconductor devices operated outside ZVS conditions are investigated at the die-level during soft-start processes at short timescales (hundreds of μs) with an infrared (IR) thermographic system. To this end, the Fourier-series time reconstruction approach is proposed and applied. By combining this technique with a SAM and a dual-channel lock-in detection, the slow thermal evolution of the die top surface is recovered with sufficient time resolution [21]. Specifically, the device under test (DUT) is a co-packaged IGBT and free-wheel diode. The paper is organized as follows: first, the ZVS and soft-start control is presented. Second, mathematical background that supports

the high thermal and time resolution of IR-acquired thermal waveforms is presented. The theoretical framework from [21] is extended to any control scheme during the SAM's heating phase, using consistent notation. Next, the test circuit, the DUTs, and the electrothermal simulation details are described. Then, simulation and experimental results are analyzed and compared. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

II. ZVS AND SOFT-START OPERATION OUTSIDE ZVS

To illustrate ZVS operation, Fig. 1(a) shows a simplified schematic of a half-bridge resonant converter. It consists of a voltage source V_{BUS} , two IGBTs with antiparallel diodes (TOP, DUT), snubber capacitors $C_{snub, TOP}$ and $C_{snub, DUT}$ across both devices, and their respective gate drivers D_{TOP} and D_{DUT} . A series RLC resonant load (L_{eq} , R_{eq} and C_{res}) is connected at the half-bridge output. The relevant waveforms are the load current I_{LOAD} , the DUT collector current I_{DUT} , and the $V_{CE, TOP}$ and V_{CE} voltages. Passive elements not essential to the discussion are omitted. The resonant load enables ZVS by delivering stored energy during the dead time t_d . The resulting I_{LOAD} first flows through the snubber capacitors, forcing $V_{CE} = 0$, and then commutates to the corresponding diode, enabling a zero-voltage turn-on. Fig. 1(b) illustrates this process: at $t = 0$, when D_{TOP} turns IGBT TOP off, the negative I_{LOAD} flows through both capacitors during the snubber interval t_{snub} . Note that the DUT is also kept off by D_{DUT} . In this interval, $C_{snub, DUT}$ is discharged and $C_{snub, TOP}$ charged. When $V_{CE} = 0$ is reached, the DUT diode conducts during t_{ZVS} . Triggering the IGBT within this interval ensures ZVS.

Operation outside the ZVS condition results in short-duration overcurrent stress ($< 1 \mu s$). ZVS loss appears when the device turns on before C_{snub} has fully discharged [Fig. 1(c)] or after diode conduction ends [10], [22], [23]. In both cases, the stored snubber energy is dissipated in the IGBT, producing a pronounced current spike and a fast V_{CE} drop. This condition arises for $f_{sw} < f_{res}$ [16] (when t_d or C_{snub} are excessively large), but also for $f_{sw} \gg f_{res}$. No die-level analysis has been reported for ZVS loss caused by $f_{sw} \gg f_{res}$, where a non-negligible charge remains on C_{snub} .

Soft-start and soft-stop intervals intrinsically force operation outside ZVS. These controlled frequency sweeps are implemented to mitigate EMI and acoustic noise [24] and commonly used in LLC converters [25]. These approaches increase or decrease the resonant current gradually by exploiting the inductive behavior of the load when $f_{sw} \gg f_{res}$. In induction-heating applications, soft-start is achieved by sweeping the switching frequency from a high initial value $f_{initial}$ down to the operating value f_{final} (and inversely for soft-stop). Since a series RLC impedance reaches its minimum at f_{res} , operating initially at $f_{sw} \gg f_{res}$ ensures low initial I_{LOAD} , which then ramps up smoothly as f_{sw} decreases. However, during these transients, the switch may turn on before V_{CE} reaches zero, causing C_{snub} to discharge through the IGBT and dissipating energy across the device active area. Soft-start intervals also occur during no-load relay commutation and low-power pulsed-operation modes.

III. FOURIER TIME RECONSTRUCTED THERMOGRAPHY IN POWER DEVICES UNDER SWITCHING CONDITIONS

Under real switching conditions, $s(t)$ represents the power dissipated in the device for any periodic modulation as

$$s(t) = v(t)i(t), \quad (1)$$

where $v(t)$ and $i(t)$ are the instantaneous voltage and currents through the device, respectively. Here, both switching and conduction losses are contemplated. By multiplying (1) with a rectangular pulse train $\Pi(t)$, defined by a heating time $t_{Heating}$ and period T_{Cycle} , the power dissipation waveform $P(t)$ under a SAM is obtained

$$P(t) = s(t)\Pi(t), \quad (2)$$

and considering the convolution theorem, the Fourier transform of $P(t)$ [$\tilde{P}(\omega)$] is written as

$$\tilde{P}(\omega) = (\tilde{s} * \tilde{\Pi})(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{s}(\omega') \tilde{\Pi}(\omega - \omega') d\omega' \quad (3)$$

where ω' is the integration variable, $\tilde{s}(\omega)$ and $\tilde{\Pi}(\omega)$ are the Fourier transforms of $s(t)$ and $\Pi(t)$, respectively. More specifically, $\tilde{\Pi}(\omega) = t_{Heating}/2 \text{sinc}(\omega t_{Heating}/(4\pi))$ is considered. Generally, in any power application, $\tilde{s}(\omega)$ can be written as a single DC component with an amplitude A_{DC} plus a continuous spectrum centered at a given frequency ω_c , $\tilde{M}_s(\omega - \omega_c)$ and $\tilde{M}_s(\omega + \omega_c)$, with an amplitude A_{AC} . This amplitude takes into account both conduction and switching losses (with the required bandwidth), i.e.,

$$\tilde{s}(\omega) = A_{DC} \delta(\omega) + A_{AC} \left(\tilde{M}_s(\omega - \omega_c) + \tilde{M}_s(\omega + \omega_c) \right). \quad (4)$$

For a fixed $t_{Heating}$ in $\tilde{\Pi}(\omega)$, T_{Cycle} is selected to allow sufficient cooling time after the die heating phase, ensuring a detectable temperature swing. In practice, $1/T_{Cycle} \ll \omega_c$, which results in virtually non-overlapping spectra for $\tilde{\Pi}(\omega)$ and $\tilde{s}(\omega)$. This allows approximating $\tilde{P}(\omega)$ as

$$\tilde{P}(\omega) \approx A_{DC} \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(l\pi d)}{l\pi} j [\delta(\omega - l\omega_0) - \delta(\omega + l\omega_0)] \right\} + A_{AC} \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(l\pi d)}{l\pi} j [\tilde{M}_s(\omega - \omega_c - l\omega_0) + \tilde{M}_s(\omega + \omega_c - l\omega_0) - \tilde{M}_s(\omega - \omega_c + l\omega_0) - \tilde{M}_s(\omega + \omega_c + l\omega_0)] \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $d = \frac{t_{Heating}}{T_{Cycle}}$, δ is the Dirac delta function, j is the imaginary unit, and l is the harmonic index of $\tilde{\Pi}(\omega)$. According to (5), $\tilde{P}(\omega)$ becomes a discretized version of $\tilde{s}(\omega)$, consisting of a DC component plus several spectral

components at l/T_{Cycle} . The electrical power $P(t)$, converted into heat in the device leads to a temperature rise on its surface $\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t)$ at a distance between each location from the coordinate origin of the thermal field (\vec{r}) and each heat source or hot spot location (\vec{r}_n). Its Fourier transform, $\Delta\tilde{T}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega)$, exhibits the corresponding discrete spectrum induced by $\tilde{P}(\omega)$

$$\Delta\tilde{T}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} \tilde{J}_n(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega) a_n \tilde{P}(\omega), \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{J}_n(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega)$ is the thermal transfer function of n -th hot spot or heat source, N_h is the total number of hot spots and a_n corresponds to a fraction of $\tilde{P}(\omega)$ dissipated in the n -th heat source. Thus, $\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t)$ can be reconstructed as a Fourier-series using the above coefficients, i.e., the spectral thermal components $\Delta\tilde{T}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega = l\omega_0)$ as

$$\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t) = \sum_{l=1}^N |\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)| \sin\left(l\omega_0 t - \frac{\pi}{4} - \arg[\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)]\right), \quad (7)$$

where $|\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)|$ and $\arg[\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)]$ are the amplitude and phase of $\Delta\tilde{T}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega = l\omega_0)$, respectively, and N is the total number of harmonics used to reconstruct $\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t)$.

$\Delta\tilde{T}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, \omega = l\omega_0)$ is determined using IR thermography as follows [21]. First, $\Pi(t)$ is implemented by periodically applying soft-start control signals to the IGBT gate with the desired modulation parameters (f_{sw} and t_d) during the heating phase ($t_{Heating}$), while keeping the device off during the cooling phase ($t_{Cooling}$). This defines the total thermal excitation period T_{Cycle} . Next, an emissivity correction process is performed to the acquired IR image sequence to obtain the true temperature map of the area inspected on top of the die [26]. Then, a lock-in procedure is applied to the true temperature images $T_k(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$, to extract the Fourier coefficient images ($\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$) at a given lock-in frequency ($f_{lock-in}$). This uses a 2-channel image correlation method, which extracts the orthogonal images corresponding to l -th harmonic, $S_l^{0^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$ and $S_l^{-90^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$, synchronized with the control signal at T_{Cycle}^{-1} , as defined in [27]

$$S_l^{0^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n) = 2 n_i^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} T_k(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n) \sin(2\pi l \phi_k), \quad (8)$$

$$S_l^{-90^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n) = -2 n_i^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} T_k(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n) \cos(2\pi l \phi_k), \quad (9)$$

where n_i is the number of acquired images and ϕ_k is the phase lag between the lock-in signal and the time instant when $T_k(x, y)$ is captured. Here, $\cos(2\pi l \phi_k)$ is equivalent to setting $f_{lock-in} = l T_{Cycle}^{-1}$ in a standard lock-in procedure to extract the l -th Fourier coefficient needed for signal time-reconstruction. After this, $|\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)|$ and $\arg[\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)]$ are calculated as [27]

$$|\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)| = \sqrt{[S_l^{0^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)]^2 + [S_l^{-90^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)]^2}, \quad (10)$$

$$\arg[\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)] = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-S_l^{-90^\circ}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)}{S_l^0(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)} \right). \quad (11)$$

Once all required Fourier coefficient images $\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$ are computed, the original waveform can be reconstructed over T_{Cycle} , i.e., t ranging from 0 to T_{Cycle} . This reconstruction is expressed in terms of $T_{Cycle}^{-1}(f_{Cycle})$ as a Fourier-series, using all determined Fourier coefficients as

$$\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t) = T_{DC}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n) + \sum_{l=1}^N |\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)| \sin(2\pi f_{Cycle} l t + \arg[\Delta\tilde{T}_l(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)]), \quad (12)$$

where $T_{DC}(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$ is the average value of all $T_k(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n)$ over the acquisition time t_{acq} . In the present case, the theoretical time resolution Δt is also limited by t_{int} due to Nyquist's sampling limit, i.e., $\Delta t = t_{int}/2$, as indicated in [21].

TABLE I. ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS OF THE POWER LOOP EMPLOYED IN THE DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS OF THE CONVERTER STUDIED IN THIS WORK.

Case study	R_{eq}	L_{eq} [μ H]	C_{res} [nF]	C_{sub} [nF]	f_{res} [kHz]
A	3.3 Ω	50/50	1080	15.0	47.1
B	SSP	214.6	78	6.8	38.9
C	SSP	90	400	15.0	26.5

TABLE II. DETAIL OF THE SOFT-START SWITCHING WAVEFORM PARAMETERS, CONTROLLING BOTH TOP AND DUT SWITCHES OF THE CONVERTER, FOR EACH CASE STUDY.

Case study	$f_{initial}$ [kHz]	f_{final} [kHz]	$t_{Heating}$ [μ s]	t_d [μ s]
A	150	75	1500	1.5
B	148.93	75	984	2.5
C	139.67	43	763	3.5

IV. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

A. DUT and IR Acquisition Setup Description

In this work, two samples of a 650 V, 40 A commercial power component designed for soft-switching converters used in induction heating were studied under soft-start driving. Each component includes a trench field-stop IGBT and a freewheeling diode in an antiparallel configuration, co-packaged in a TO-247 housing. As main DUT electrical parameters, the IGBT exhibits a typical saturation voltage of 1.45 V at the operating point: $I_{DUT} = 40$ A and gate-emitter voltage $V_{GE} = 15$ V. The device has a typical gate-threshold voltage of 5.5 V, measured at $V_{GE} = V_{CE}$ and $I_{DUT} = 40$ mA. The typical input capacitance is 1982 pF at 1 MHz, for $V_{CE} = 30$ V and $V_{GE} = 0$ V. Regarding its thermal characteristics, the device provides a maximum junction-to-case thermal resistance of 0.56 $^{\circ}$ C/W and a maximum allowable junction temperature of 175 $^{\circ}$ C. Additional device specifications are provided in [28]. For preparing the DUT for IR measurements, a window was opened on top of its molding compound to provide a direct optical path to the dies. To enhance IR camera sensitivity, the chips were coated with a high-emissivity material.

In order to monitor and study local stress areas by current crowding as hot spots, infrared (IR) measurements were

conducted using a FLIR SC5500 IR camera (wavelength range: 2.5-5.1 μ m) equipped with an internal lock-in module. To inspect the region of interest over the die surface, the G3x lens was used, providing a field of view of 3.2 x 2.4 mm. Key camera settings included a frame rate of 376 Hz, chosen to minimize read-out noise [16], [21]. An integration time of 24 μ s was set for case studies B and C, and extended to 49 μ s for case A due to the lower bandwidth of the temperature response, enhancing SNR. Thanks to the Fourier-based approach, the camera can resolve thermal events on the microsecond scale. The time resolution Δt is determined by the integration time, i.e., $\Delta t = t_{int}/2$ [21], as noted in III. While the camera's presence may slightly alter heat convection from the device, this effect is neglectable for three reasons.: First, hotspots form much earlier than convection begins. Second, lock-in analysis minimizes boundary influences. Third, thermal images show no optical distortion due to mirage effect.

The DUT was mounted on a Peltier thermo-regulated micro-positioning stage with five degrees of freedom (X-Y-Z positioning, rotation, and tilt). This stage also heats the DUT to an initial operating temperature (T_i) to enhance the SNR of the IR images. The heating was controlled by a Linkam PE120 Peltier stage and managed through a Linkam T95-PE controller, enabling T_i to be set between -25 $^{\circ}$ C and 125 $^{\circ}$ C. In case A, it was set to 65 $^{\circ}$ C to reflect the system's medium-range operating temperature. In cases B and C, T_i was set to 110 $^{\circ}$ C. This simulates the maximum operating temperature of 130 $^{\circ}$ C, with a 20 $^{\circ}$ C margin.

B. Converter and Soft-Start SAM Description

To operate the DUT under soft-start SAM driving, the converter presented in the schematic of Fig. 2(a) is used. In this figure, collector and emitter parasitic inductances (L_C and L_E) for each device are included, as they are used in simulations of VI. Likewise, the parasitics $R_{p,1}$, $R_{p,2}$, and $L_{p,1}$ (in green) compensate for limitations in the IGBT model in simulations of VI, as explained in V.

This converter is a slight modification of the standard half-bridge series resonant topology employed in induction cooktops. It incorporates an auxiliary IGBT (AUX) placed in series with the DUT. This configuration enables accurate conduction losses measurements by overcoming the oscilloscope's dynamic range limitations [16]. Switching the AUX at f_{sw} while holding the DUT on, the AUX blocks the high V_{BUS} . This significantly reduces the measurement range required to properly resolve the DUT's on-state voltage. In this work, the AUX device is kept permanently on to allow the IR camera to capture current-crowding effects in the DUT during real switching operation. The resulting thermal maps reflect the current distribution around the emitter bonding contacts, where current crowding occurs as the current exits the device. To ensure this behavior, AUX is forced into a constant on-state with D_{AUX} . Under these conditions, the circuit operates as a standard half-bridge series resonant inverter (HB SRI).

The schematic of Fig. 2 (a) also presents the rest of components commonly found in HB SRIs. First, Fig. 2 (a) shows the snubber capacitors ($C_{sub,1}$ and $C_{sub,2}$) in parallel with the power devices. The C_{sub} reduces the dissipated

Fig. 2. (a) Test circuit schematic consisting in a modified half-bridge with attached RLC resonant load; sign convention of I_{LOAD} and I_{DUT} as displayed. Green-colored components are exclusive to the simulation; L_C & L_E represent the internal IGBT parasitic inductances. (b) Soft-start control waveforms ($f_{initial} > f_{final}$) at the top switch and the DUT, the instantaneous frequency follows a linear trend with respect to time. (c) Equivalent thermal circuit schematic and values used in the electro-thermal simulations – R in [K/W] and C in [J/K].

power during the switch turn-off and prevents device damage. Second, three isolated IGBT gate drivers (D_{TOP} , D_{AUX} and D_{DUT}) control each IGBT gate via $R_G = 10 \Omega$ gate resistors, with $V_{GE} = 20 \text{ V}$. Third, the half-bridge output is connected to a load consisting of a resistor (R_{eq}), an inductor (L_{eq}) and a capacitor (C_{res}) in series. This resonant load determines the frequency-dependent behavior of the voltage and current through the DUT, with its natural resonance frequency f_{res} defined as $f_{res} = (4\pi^2 L_{eq} C_{res})^{-1/2}$. Finally, V_{BUS} and BUS capacitor (C_{BUS}) are the last part of the HB SRI. Usually, V_{BUS} in an induction cooktop varies following the rectified waveform of the mains. In the performed tests, a constant V_{BUS} , stabilized with a large electrolytic C_{BUS} (1500 μF , 450 V rated), is set to $V_{BUS} = 325 \text{ V}$ (230 V RMS) with a Chroma 62150H-1000 source. This value fixes a worst-case scenario, as higher dissipation is expected at the peak mains voltage.

The analysis will be focused on the soft-start, as the symmetrical soft-stop process is expected to provide similar temperature increases. Fig. 2(b) depicts the soft-start driving implementation with a SAM. During soft-start operation, a square waveform with V_{GE} ranging from 0 to 20 V and a linear frequency sweep from $f_{initial}$ to f_{final} is applied to the DUT. The complementary waveform with the specified t_d is applied to the TOP device. The resulting modulation for the TOP and DUT devices can be observed in Fig. 2(b). To implement the SAM, the soft-start driving is applied during $t_{Heating}$ (heating phase). Then, switching is stopped, and both devices are left in the blocking state to allow the DUT to cool during $t_{Cooling}$, until the end of $T_{Cycle} = 10 \text{ ms}$ [cooling phase, see Fig. 2(b)]. Before measuring with the camera, several SAM cycles are applied to reach thermal steady-state. Due to the complexity of the soft-start SAM scheme, the driving signals were generated using a computer program and implemented with an arbitrary waveform generator (Agilent 33522A).

C. Case Studies Description

In this work, three representative case studies replicate key soft-start processes observed in commercial induction

hobs, optimizing cookware heating efficiency by varying the inductor technology. In case study A, two circular inductors, each matching a medium-to-large pot's footprint are connected in parallel (21 cm, 50 μH each), resulting in 10.54 μH . Case A operates the DUT under ZVS condition during all $t_{Heating}$ without turn-on losses, and is used as a reference. In case study B, a single hexagonal inductor with a smaller diameter (7.3 cm, 214.6 μH), employed normally in a matrix arrangement, is studied. This matrix configuration of smaller inductors offers more flexible cookware positioning than the fixed large inductors in case A. Case B stresses the DUT by operating outside ZVS during the major part of $t_{Heating}$ with higher turn-on losses. In case C, a single rectangular inductor (20 \times 8.7 cm², 90 μH), part of a row-based setup for flexible cookware use, is studied. This row-based distribution adapts to various cookware by activating only the covered inductors. Case C confines the operation outside ZVS to the $t_{Heating}$ initial part.

To set the DUT operation within or outside ZVS for each case study, the values required for L_{eq} , R_{eq} , C_{snub} and C_{res} are listed in Table I. The R_{eq} was implemented differently: as a fixed bank of power resistors connected in series to the loop ($R_{eq} = 3.3 \Omega$); or as a stainless-steel pot (SSP) placed on top of the glass-ceramic surface, with the L_{eq} inductor beneath. Table II specifies the driving and SAM modulation parameters. The same inductors and capacitors installed by the cooktop manufacturer were employed in all cases, ensuring an equivalent electrical behavior.

V. SOFT-START ELECTRO-THERMAL MODELING

A. SPICE Simulation Description

To complement experimental results and relate current crowding to the DUT's surface thermal distribution, the schematic of Fig. 2(a) was simulated with LT-Spice as follows. For the electrical part, all the parasitic elements highlighted in green in Fig. 2(a) were accounted for. The manufacturer's standard IGBT electrical model was considered. The power supply was treated as ideal due to the large C_{BUS} and additional decoupling capacitors. L_C and

L_E were set at 15 nH and 2 nH, respectively. Lastly, the values specified in Tables I-II were considered for each case study.

For the DUT's thermal model, the fifth-order Cauer network depicted in Fig. 2(c) was derived from junction-to-Peltier thermal impedance measurements. The thermal stack includes the TO-247 package, multiple thermal interface material (TIM) layers, an Al_2O_3 slab, a copper baseplate, and the Peltier aluminum plate. Parameter extraction, performed in reference [16], was carried out in two steps. First, the standard method was used to obtain thermal impedance from junction to copper baseplate via electrical measurements during cooldown after a 22 W pulse. Second, IR imaging was employed to measure the area-averaged T_j to extend the model to the Peltier stage [$Z_{th(j-p)}$], due to limitations in measuring its temperature electrically. Because the IR camera lacked sufficient time resolution below 1 ms, its data was combined with the first step results. The resulting curves were merged and fitted with a fifth-order equation and converted to RC Cauer network parameters, as shown in Fig. 2(c). This results in a linear thermal model with an acceptable expected relative error below 3 %. This linear model works as the temperature excursions in this work remain below 60 °C [29]. This removes the need for a non-linear thermal model. Note that SPICE simulations estimate temperature evolution (ΔT_{sim}) using a one-dimensional Cauer thermal model based on averaged chip-level measurements. To preserve the independence of the comparison, ΔT_{sim} is used solely as a reference against IR imaging results.

To assess the accuracy of thermal predictions, simulated and measured dissipated power waveforms ($P_{DUT,sim}$ and $P_{DUT,meas}$, respectively) were determined and compared. With $P_{DUT,sim}$ and $P_{DUT,meas}$, the corresponding temperature increases, ΔT_{sim} and $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$, were computed with the DUT's network model. Using $P_{DUT,sim}$ mitigates dynamic-range, time-resolution, and switching-noise limitations present in $P_{DUT,meas}$. These effects distort the thermal predictions, as noted in VI.

B. Simulation Accuracy and Time Reduction

Further efforts were made to match simulated and measured electrical waveforms in each case study and to reduce the required computation time. The manufacturer IGBT SPICE model showed reduced accuracy, as it produced a faster dynamic response and higher transconductance than the real device. This led to exaggerated collector-current peaks under non-ZVS switching. These discrepancies were corrected in the DUT with all the parasitics shown in black and green in Fig. 2 (a). With these components, electrical simulations were refined to obtain $P_{DUT,sim}$ without acquisition limitations, e.g., oscilloscope vertical and time scale limits. Subsequently, these parasitics were adjusted in two steps to match simulations with measured electrical data. First, the load, $C_{snub,2}$, and key parasitics were adjusted to match the simulated I_{LOAD} and I_{DUT} waveforms to the measured ones. The load and $C_{snub,2}$ were set to reproduce the measured f_{res} and I_{LOAD} . $L_{p,1}$ shaped the I_{DUT} dynamics, whereas $R_{p,1}$ reduced its amplitude. Second, the device parasitics were

further adjusted by modifying the inductance values of bonding wires and external leads (i.e., $L_{C,i}$ and $L_{E,i}$). $R_{p,2}$ was considered to reduce V_{CE} to match the dissipated power in the simulations, as discussed further on. In fact, electrical SPICE results were used to deduce the dissipated power (see VI.B-VI.C).

To reduce computation time, the thermal transient before reaching steady state is approximated as a linear temperature evolution. This is possible thanks to the larger thermal time constants, which are significantly longer than T_{Cycle} . In this approach, the initial and final T_{Cycle} temperatures define the interval over which a linear fit models the temperature change. Subtracting this fit from the simulated transient waveform yields the steady-state response, thereby significantly decreasing simulation time.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Criteria for results interpretation

The data is presented and discussed for each case study according to the following steps. First, to improve interpretability, the temperature rise ΔT was calculated by subtracting, for each pixel, its minimum value over time. Second, to ensure consistency across all case studies, four overheated areas were defined. Third, within each region, the hottest pixels during the heating phase were identified and monitored. Finally, when one of the monitored pixels reaches the highest peak temperature, the corresponding thermal map image was extracted. Besides, the overheated regions were highlighted using white dotted lines.

To compare experimental and SPICE thermal results, a statistical analysis was performed on the active device area, excluding the edge termination and emitter contacts. The mean, mode, and standard deviation (σ) of the temperature distribution across the active area were computed at each time instant. In fact, σ serves as an accuracy indicator for thermal models. Adjusting the integer scaling factor n_σ until the peak matches the simulated temperature waveform quantifies deviations between experimental and simulated results. A larger n_σ indicates greater dispersion. These statistical parameters have physical significance. At the considered timescales, bonding wires do not heat the die. Instead, surface heat sources follow minimum impedance paths, causing current crowding. Heat diffuses from these areas, forming a spatial thermal map. The mean, mode, and σ characterize this distribution, with higher σ indicating greater non-uniformity and vice versa. Furthermore, the degree of similarity between the mode and average values informs about the distribution symmetry and, in turn, about temperature inhomogeneities due to current crowding.

As a metric for assessing current crowding, a parameter based on the ratio between temperature deviation and average temperature μ (σ/μ), known in statistics as the variation coefficient, is proposed. Here, the thermal σ/μ ratio accounts for temperature dispersion across the active area. It also offers a metric to quantify the current distribution with a single number, which enables the comparison among all case studies proposed in III.C. Unfortunately, the σ/μ ratio is highly noise-sensitive, particularly when the μ or σ values do not exceed the image

Fig. 3. Case A results: (a) electrical waveforms; (b) detailed view of (a); (c) waveforms of $P_{DUT,sim}$, $P_{DUT,meas}$, ΔT_{sim} and $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$; (d) die top picture with thermal map and pixel locations at inspected area; (e) IR thermal evolution at four pixels; and (f) comparison of mean and mode temperatures (variance added $\pm n_\sigma\sigma$) with ΔT_{sim} .

noise level. This occurs at immediately before or after device biasing, or when the device is nearly cooled down, as σ/μ ratio may become indeterminate or yield unreliable results. To address this, a modified thermal variation coefficient (CV) is redefined to improve robustness under these conditions, as:

$$CV = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma}{mN_{rms}} & \text{if } \mu < mN_{rms} \\ \frac{\sigma}{\mu} & \text{if } \mu \geq mN_{rms} \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

where N_{rms} is the thermal image RMS noise, and m is a scaling factor to fix a threshold noise value to mitigate inaccurate or unrealistic CV values.

To relate it with current distribution, lower (higher) CV values indicate more uniform (localized) conduction and reduced (higher) current crowding. As discussed further on, CV depends on the time evolution of μ and σ , each governed by distinct physical mechanisms and averaged over t_{int} . With this new definition, the noise level N_{rms} in the thermal image fixes a minimum CV measurable with the camera (CV_{min}). For this analysis, the timescale is a key parameter as t_{int} fixes the thermal sensitivity, acquisition time and N_{rms} .

Discrepancies between experimental and SPICE results are expected. The thermal model is based on a cooling process starting from steady-state thermal and electrical conditions, ensuring a uniform conduction and in turn, heat dissipation. Bonding wires also influence heating and play a key role in heat extraction. This differs from the conditions outside ZVS operation, where current crowding may occur. Once conduction stops during thermal-impedance measurements, the internal heat sources and temperature distribution may diverge from those in

non-ZVS operation. However, their magnitudes remain within the same order of magnitude.

B. Case A

Fig. 3 summarizes all results for case A. Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) compare simulated and measured electrical waveforms, obtaining an excellent match. This agreement was found by setting L_{eq} to $10.54 \mu\text{H}$ and $R_{eq} = 3.6 \Omega$ to reproduce f_{res} and reduce I_{LOAD} , respectively. As Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) depict, the DUT operates within ZVS throughout the soft-start process. In this interval, I_{DUT} closely follows I_{LOAD} , except for a high-frequency ringing in the diode current not present in I_{LOAD} . Fig. 3 (c) compares the waveforms of $P_{DUT,meas}$ with $P_{DUT,sim}$ and $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$ with ΔT_{sim} . With this, the measurement limitations affecting $P_{DUT,meas}$ and their influence on the thermal predictions are quantified. The good agreement between $P_{DUT,meas}$ and $P_{DUT,sim}$ validates the electrical model. In contrast, ΔT_{sim} evolves more linearly than $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$, as limiting factors inherent to $P_{DUT,meas}$ measurement are compensated in $P_{DUT,sim}$. For this reason, IR thermal measurements are compared to ΔT_{sim} in V.B, V.C and V.D.

As for IR thermal measurements, Fig. 3(d) presents the DUT's thermal image when maximum ΔT is achieved. It highlights current crowding near the emitter bonding wires in the lower right region of the IGBT die. This area is critical for both current distribution and device reliability, consistent with [16]. The temperature distribution further indicates minimal heating between the bonding wires. This suggests low current conduction between them due to their close spacing, effectively merging them into a single contact as observed in [16]. The overheated areas 2, 3 and 4 are defined by the shielding effect of the two bonding wires blocking the camera lens. This thermal distribution is crucial to understand the current crowding evolution. Fig. 3(e) analyzes the evolution of the four overheated areas

identified in Fig. 3(d) through the hottest pixel in each region, and compares these values with ΔT_{sim} . Pixels 1 and 3 show similar temperature trends, but Pixel 1 reaches a higher temperature. Pixel 2, located below the lowest emitter bonding wire, has a slower initial increase than Pixel 1 but ultimately achieves the highest temperature. This is due to its proximity to the shortest bonding wire, indicating shortest current path (i.e., the lowest electrical impedance). Pixel 4 depicts the lowest temperature increase. The varying thermal dynamics among these pixels are influenced by the driving scheme and electrical waveforms presented in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). Fig. 3(e) also shows that Pixels 1 to 4 reach their peak temperature at $t = t_{\text{Heating}}$. As Fig. 3(a) indicates, I_{DUT} peaks increase from 20 to 40 A, linearly rising power dissipation over time. Initially, higher f_{sw} concentrates conduction in Areas 1 and 2, as they provide the shortest current path. However, as f_{sw} decreases, current spreads across Areas 3 and 4 [see Fig. 3(e)]. This causes Pixels 1 and 2 to peak earlier than Pixels 3 and 4. Additionally, Pixels 3 and 4 peak after the end of t_{Heating} because they are located in regions with higher thermal and electrical impedance, mainly due to the longer bonding wires to the package terminals. All in all, from a thermal perspective the lower than 6 °C observed ΔT values are safe for the device reliability. As for the simulated temperature waveform, ΔT_{sim} shows a good agreement with experimental results during the heating phase. During the cooling down, ΔT_{sim} decays faster compared with the experimental results, likely due to differences in thermal model accuracy resulting from its extraction (uniform or localized current conduction). Despite these discrepancies, the maximum value and overall shape of ΔT_{sim} agree with measurements.

To assess experimental results, Fig. 3(f) compares the mean and mode analyses of measured temperatures with ΔT_{sim} . This figure also includes the error bars representing a variance $\pm n_{\sigma}\sigma$ ($n_{\sigma} = 2$). As a first observation, mean, mode and ΔT_{sim} show good agreement, with the simulations falling within the interval defined by $\pm 2\sigma$. The similarity between the mean and mode values suggests a symmetric spatial distribution. This indicates a Gaussian-like behavior, consistent with heat conduction in solids. It also demonstrates that ZVS operation promotes an almost uniform current distribution across the overheated areas.

C. Case B

Fig. 4 summarizes the main results of case B. Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) compare simulated and measured electrical waveforms at different timescales, obtaining an excellent match that validates the electrical model. Unlike case A, case B operates the device outside the ZVS condition for a long part of the soft-start process (900 μs). In the last 100 μs , the device operates under ZVS condition because f_{sw} has been sufficiently reduced [see Fig. 4(b)]. Despite this, this process is successfully completed without causing damage or degradation to the device, as seen in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b). Outside the ZVS condition, the I_{DUT} presents a spike-like waveform, initially reaching peaks of 30 A; while I_{LOAD} remains below 1.7 A. The electrical simulation results enable the calculation of $P_{\text{DUT,sim}}$ to be compared with $P_{\text{DUT,meas}}$, as depicted in Fig. 4(c). Fig. 4(c) also shows ΔT_{sim}

and $\Delta T_{\text{meas,osc}}$. This match between simulations and measurements in Figs. 4(a)-4(c) was achieved using L_{eq} nominal value and $R_{\text{p},1} = 1.5 \Omega$, to decrease I_{DUT} and thus P_{DUT} . In addition, $L_{\text{C}} = 19.4 \text{ nH}$ and $L_{\text{S}} = 22 \text{ nH}$ were set.

As for IR thermal measurements, Fig. 4(d) presents the DUT's thermal image when maximum ΔT is achieved, defining the overheated areas and monitored pixels. Regarding the spots marked in Fig. 4(d), Pixel 2 exhibits the largest ΔT in Fig. 4(e) similar to case A. Pixel 3 shows the second-largest ΔT but with the slowest ΔT evolution. According to Fig. 4(c), P_{DUT} experiences a minimum at $t = 700 \mu\text{s}$. At this instant, Pixels 1, 2 and 4 reach their maximum temperature, while Pixel 3 presents a delay. Pixel 3 peaks at $t = 870 \mu\text{s}$ due to its greater distance from the shortest current path regions. Pixels 1 and 4 display the same response during the heat-up, but Pixel 1 cools down slightly faster due to the enhanced heat extraction by the bonding wires. Regarding the temperature distribution in Fig. 4(d), the same observation made in case A applies here. Low current conduction occurs between both bonding wires, although this case exhibits an even lower temperature increase. Despite being a different device, the similar separation of both bonding contacts allows for the same reasoning to be applied. From a reliability standpoint and considering only the thermal magnitude, the measured values of $\Delta T < 1.6 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are negligible.

As in case A, Fig. 4(e) compares Pixels 1, 2, 3 and 4 with ΔT_{sim} . ΔT_{sim} evolves faster and achieves higher values than those measured. The fast power transients outside ZVS operation, predominant in case B, contrast with the homogeneous current distribution assumed during thermal model extraction. Consequently, case A, operating within ZVS, shows better agreement between simulation and measured temperatures than case B. To provide deeper insight, Fig. 4(f) compares the mean and mode analyses with ΔT_{sim} , using $n_{\sigma} = 5$ and $n_{\sigma} = 3$, respectively. The larger n_{σ} compared to case A indicates greater deviation from ΔT_{sim} . Additionally, the large difference between the mode and mean values indicates a non-symmetric spatial distribution. This behavior reveals localized hotspots caused by current crowding during operation outside ZVS. The mode values show closer agreement with the simulations. Overall, the lower agreement compared with case A is attributed to current crowding effects originated from non-ZVS operation.

D. Case C

Fig. 5 summarizes all results for case C. As presented in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b), the DUT initially operates outside ZVS but enters ZVS at $t = 300 \mu\text{s}$, earlier than in case B. This represents an intermediate case between cases A and B in terms of current and temperature homogeneity. As noted in IV.A, electrical adjustments were required to match measured waveforms outside ZVS. Specifically, a time-dependent resistance $R_{\text{p},2}$ was added in parallel with $C_{\text{s,sub},2}$ to align V_{CE} waveforms at the turn-on instant with measurements, and the DUT was modified with a series inductance $L_{\text{p},1} = 48.9 \text{ nH}$ and a series resistance $R_{\text{p},1} = 1.5 \Omega$ to decrease I_{DUT} and tailor its dynamic behavior. Fig. 5(c) compares simulated and measured

Fig. 4. Case B results: (a) electrical waveforms; (b) detailed view of (a); (c) waveforms of $P_{DUT,sim}$, $P_{DUT,meas}$, ΔT_{sim} and $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$; (d) IR thermal image with areas and pixel locations; (e) IR thermal evolution at four pixels; (f) comparison of mean and mode temperatures (variance added $\pm n_\sigma\sigma$) with ΔT_{sim} .

Fig. 5. Case C results: (a) electrical waveforms; (b) detailed view of (a); (c) measured and simulated electrical waveforms during a single pulse; (d) waveforms of $P_{DUT,sim}$, $P_{DUT,meas}$, ΔT_{sim} and $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$ (inset: thermal image with areas and pixel locations); (e) comparison of mean and mode temperatures (variance added $\pm n_\sigma\sigma$) with ΔT_{sim} .

waveforms for a single turn-on pulse during the soft-start process. This figure shows that while the results match well on the microsecond scale, deviations become noticeable at shorter timescales. This discrepancy is due to the IGBT electrical model inaccuracy. The turn-on process of the model presents a smooth evolution of $I_{DUT,sim}$ and $V_{CE,sim}$. In contrast, the measured behavior exhibits a rapid initial rise in $I_{DUT,meas}$ similar to $I_{DUT,sim}$, followed by a slower evolution of $I_{DUT,meas}$ and $V_{CE,meas}$. This divergence is caused by the V_{GE} plateau, which is not predicted by the simulation model.

In this case, the intrinsic limitations of the IGBT SPICE model could only be partially overcome with external parasitic components. Based on these values, Fig. 5 (d)

shows significant differences between the measured and simulated power waveforms $P_{DUT,meas}$ and $P_{DUT,sim}$, and consequently between the calculated $\Delta T_{meas,osc}$ and ΔT_{sim} . According to Fig. 5(a), I_{DUT} peaks at 25 A initially and 15 A at the end of the soft-start period. This results in a complex temperature waveform with two local maxima. The first one is caused by the higher initial power dissipation from turn-on losses during non-ZVS operation. The second one is due to the lower power dissipation mainly from conduction losses as I_{LOAD} increases. This pattern is reflected in the simulation result (ΔT_{sim}), showing two temperature peaks within the soft-start process.

As for thermal measurements, the inset of Fig. 5(e)

defines the overheated areas and monitored pixels as in cases A and B, observing a similar behavior. Fig. 5(e) indicates a high ΔT slope for all pixels before the first ΔT_{sim} peak during non-ZVS switching, and a reduced slope between the first and second peaks. Pixels 1 and 4 exhibit a similar evolution, showing the lowest ΔT values among the measured pixels, with Pixel 1 presenting a faster cool down, consistent with case B and leading to the same applicable conclusions. Pixel 2, located below the left emitter bonding wire, reaches the highest value. Compared with Pixel 2, Pixel 3 shows a similar response and a slightly lower maximum value. This behavior follows the same pattern observed in cases A and B. Pixels 1, 2 and 4 reach their maximum ΔT at the same time instant, with Pixel 3 presenting a delay for the same reasons. Overall, from the thermal point of view, device lifetime is expected to remain unaltered with the measured $\Delta T < 0.8$ °C values. Despite simulation adjustments, ΔT_{sim} showed a lower first peak than $\Delta T_{meas.osc}$, although both reached a maximum of approximately 0.6 °C. During the first temperature peak, the model predicts a different ΔT_{sim} evolution than measurements. This is due to electrical model limitations [see Fig. 5(c)] and non-ZVS operation. However, as in case A, a good match is obtained at the second temperature peak, as the device is ZVS operated after the first peak.

Fig. 5(f) compares ΔT_{sim} with the mean and mode analyses, showing that the mode aligns more closely with ΔT_{sim} . Statistical analysis indicates that, with $n_\sigma = 1$, the simulated ΔT_{sim} predicts the thermal evolution much more accurately than in case B. This improvement results from the shorter time spent operating outside ZVS, which is more consistent with the conditions used to extract the $Z_{th(j-p)}$ model.

TABLE III. MINIMUM - MAXIMUM TEMPERATURES (IN °C) INSIDE EACH OVERHEATED AREA AT THE MAXIMUM TEMPERATURE TIME INSTANT.

Case study	Area 1	Area 2	Area 3	Area 4
A	2.76-5.69	2.84-5.90	2.76-5.63	2.03-4.27
B	0.67-1.40	0.66-1.50	0.69-1.46	0.60-1.40
C	0.30-0.63	0.29-0.77	0.29-0.74	0.27-0.61

E. Current Crowding Analysis

Based on the thermal images shown in Figs. 3(d), 4(d), 5(e), Table III summarizes for each case study, the minimum and maximum values measured within each overheated area. From this table, all values range from 0.27 °C to 5.90 °C, reflecting a non-homogenous temperature variation related to current crowding phenomena. Table III also provides the order of magnitude of these variations. Although the absolute temperature variations detailed in Table III (≤ 6 °C) may appear small, their significance lies in their spatial non-uniformity rather than in their magnitude. Hotter regions correspond to localized increases in current density, which are characteristic of current crowding phenomena.

As discussed in VI.A, CV is used to derive from the thermal images a normalized and dimensionless indicator of current crowding for each case study. Figure 6 shows the time evolution of the CV metric for all cases. Specifically, Fig. 6(a) presents, for each case study, the evolution of CV

(scatter plot) and f_{sw} (dotted lines); also highlighting the CV_{min} value (horizontal solid lines) and the time instant $t_{Heating}$ (vertical dashed lines). Additionally, the μ and σ evolution for each case is presented in log-log scale in Fig. 6(b), to assist with the interpretation of the results reported in Fig. 6(a). A general analysis of the CV evolution, valid for all cases, can be made as follows. From 10 μs to 80 μs , CV transitions from a homogeneous thermal map (i.e., CV_{min} value) to an increasingly uneven distribution due to current crowding. This evolution stabilizes, reaching a plateau at 100 μs for case A and 150 μs for cases B and C. As already shown, the hotspot location, dictated by both the device design and bonding wire pad location, is the same for all cases [see Figs. 3(d), 4(d), 5(e)]. During this plateau, μ and σ increase at similar rates, keeping CV almost constant, as shown in Fig. 6(b) via the logarithmic relation $\log(CV) = \log(\sigma) - \log(\mu)$. This behavior stems from the current distribution, which has been established during the initial heat up of the device. After the plateau, CV decreases as temperature distribution becomes more uniform. Namely, μ rises faster than σ since deeper packaging layers and heatsink heat up and uniformly increase the die temperature. During device turn-off ($t_{Heating}$), cases A and C show slope changes in μ and σ , with CV presenting a local minimum slightly later. Case B shows unique turn-off behavior. Although $t_{Heating}$ marks the end of dissipation at 984 μs , power drops steadily since the beginning and becomes negligible by 700 μs due to ZVS operation. Some pixels reach peak temperature earlier, and μ and σ show no sharp slope change at $t_{Heating}$, instead following the smooth decline of P_{DUT} . Generally, in this final phase, CV becomes less informative, as both μ and σ shift together due to thermal interface effects. Then, the most representative indicator of current crowding at the die level is the CV plateau, as it reflects the current distribution homogeneity averaged over t_{int} . For timescales below 100 μs , the CV does not depend on t_{int} . This outcome demonstrates the robustness of the CV definition against the N_{rms} level.

Focusing on the CV plateau in Fig. 6(a), analysis reveals that case A shows the highest temperature inhomogeneity, contrary to initial expectations of a uniform response due to ZVS operation. Under this operation, the device presents higher conduction losses compared with cases B and C. This increases the current density in the defined areas in Figs. 3(d), 4(d), 5(e). Additionally, case A maintains the highest f_{sw} throughout soft-start, further contributing to higher switching losses. Cases B and C exhibit similar plateau values but differ slightly in their subsequent evolution due to variations in their dissipation schemes. Case B reaches a CV peak at around 150 μs , indicating an intermediate current crowding between cases A and C. This coincides with high P_{DUT} pulses (~ 2 kW), which subsequently decrease, following the same trend as CV . This suggests that initial power pulses induce current inhomogeneity, but as the dissipated power level decreases, it becomes insufficient to sustain this effect. After this peak, case C surpasses B, with its CV maximum occurring during the transition from non-ZVS to ZVS operation, following several high-power pulses. Despite entering ZVS condition, CV remains stable due to turn-off losses and begins to

Fig. 6. (a) CV evolution per case study, including the CV_{min} value in solid lines, f_{sw} and $t_{heating}$ time in dashed lines. (b) μ (solid lines) and σ (dashed lines) evolution with time for each case study.

decrease around 800 μ s as soft-start ends.

F. Current Crowding Mitigation

Several strategies can be proposed to mitigate current crowding effects at the converter, packaging, and device levels. At the converter level, the priority is to achieve soft-start/stop while maintaining Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) and limiting energy surges in both the RLC network and the switching device. The most effective approach is to initiate inverter modulation at $V_{BUS} = 0$ V by implementing a bus-discharge circuit. Another option is to employ an active snubber circuit presenting a lower-than-nominal C_{snub} value during soft-start, greatly reducing the peak of the short time overcurrent event. This approach could be implemented with a solid-state switch in series with C_{snub} , following the topology reviewed in [30]. Alternative options include adjusting the RLC components to extend the ZVS frequency range or adding a buck converter to ramp up V_{BUS} . In the latter, the converter must be located between the DC power supply and the V_{BUS} node of the inverter. Obviously, this solution substantially increases the cost of the appliance.

From the power device package point of view, two options are available. First, the location of the emitter bonding contacts should be optimized to distribute more efficiently the current during transient operation. Second, the junction to case thermal impedance should be improved to reduce the peak temperature of the hotspots.

Finally, at the chip level, the design of the IGBT basic cells surrounding the emitter contacts can be modified to

reduce their tendency to conduct higher currents along the lowest-impedance paths. This can be achieved by intentionally delaying their turn-on time according to the device's switching frequency. Additionally, increasing the number of gate runner sections or optimizing their layout can further mitigate current crowding.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Infrared (IR) imaging combined with external device modulation has been demonstrated as an effective technique for analyzing current crowding in IGBTs under real operating conditions. The experiments have revealed that transient switching outside zero-voltage switching (ZVS) at 100 kHz has produced highly non-uniform heat generation within the die. These thermal gradients have developed on sub-100 μ s timescales and have originated hot spots associated with current crowding. The peak temperature has consistently appeared near the left emitter bonding wire, which has exhibited lower electrical impedance and therefore has conducted a larger share of the current.

Electrothermal SPICE simulations have shown good agreement with the measurements, with errors remaining within a 5σ worst-case range. However, the mismatch has increased with time outside ZVS, indicating that conduction has become increasingly non-homogeneous. Finally, when the IGBTs are operated outside ZVS, the statistical mode of IR temperature values has correlated more closely with simulation results than mean temperature values. This suggests that under non-ZVS condition, junction temperatures inferred from thermo-sensitive electrical parameters reflect the statistical mode of the die temperature rather than the mean.

As next steps, the proposed IR methodology has enabled the analysis of fast stressful events and could support the development of intra-die thermal models for IGBTs. Although further work is required, this approach shows promise for extension to other power devices.

REFERENCES

- [1] Clark W. Gellings, "Chapter 10 BENEFICIAL RESIDENTIAL BUILDING USES OF ELECTRICITY," in *Saving Energy and Reducing CO2 Emissions with Electricity*, River Publishers, 2011, pp.227-238.
- [2] T. Mai, D. Steinberg, J. Logan, D. Bielen, K. Eurek and C. McMillan, "An Electrified Future: Initial Scenarios and Future Research for U.S. Energy and Electricity Systems," in *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 34-47, July-Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1109/MPE.2018.2820445.
- [3] S. T. Nguyen and N. A. Ho-Tran, "An Investigation on Energy Efficiency of Infrared and Induction Cooktops," *2020 Applying New Technology in Green Buildings (ATiGB)*, 2021, pp. 115-119, doi: 10.1109/ATiGB50996.2021.9423196.
- [4] M. Aoyama, W. Thimm, M. Knoch and L. Ose, "Proposal and Challenge of Halbach Array Type Induction Coil for Cooktop Applications," in *IEEE Open Journal of Industry Applications*, vol. 2, pp. 168-177, 2021, doi: 10.1109/OJIA.2021.3092972.
- [5] H. Sarnago, P. Guillén, J. M. Burdío and O. Lucia, "Multiple-Output ZVS Resonant Inverter Architecture for Flexible Induction Heating Appliances," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 157046-157056, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2950346.
- [6] G. Bartolozzi, G. Palma, and A. Rizzo, "Energy saving starts in the kitchen," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 322, pp. 114726-114726, Nov. 2024, doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114726.
- [7] M. Kwon, S. H. Kang, Y. Seong Hwang and B. K. Lee, "Enhanced Efficiency Improvement Scheme for Domestic Induction Cooktop

- Using Variable DC-Link Voltage Control," *2023 11th International Conference on Power Electronics and ECCE Asia (ICPE 2023 - ECCE Asia)*, Jeju Island, Korea, Republic of, 2023, pp. 1992-1997, doi: 10.23919/ICPE2023-ECCEAsia54778.2023.10213710.
- [8] V. Esteve, José Jordán, and J. L. Bellido, "Optimizing the Efficiency of Series Resonant Half-Bridge Inverters for Induction Heating Applications," *Electronics*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 1200–1200, Mar. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics14061200>.
- [9] M. Ozturk, S. Aslan, N. Altintas and S. Sinirlioglu, "Comparison of Induction Cooker Power Converters," *2018 6th International Conference on Control Engineering & Information Technology (CEIT)*, 2018, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/CEIT.2018.8751920.
- [10] O. Lucía, P. Maussion, E. J. Dede and J. M. Burdío, "Induction Heating Technology and Its Applications: Past Developments, Current Technology, and Future Challenges," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 5, pp. 2509-2520, May 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2013.2281162.
- [11] H. Mahdi, B. Hoff and T. Østrem, "A Review of Power Converters for Ships Electrification," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 4680-4697, April 2023, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2022.3227398.
- [12] A. J. Hanson and D. J. Perreault, "A High-Frequency Power Factor Correction Stage With Low Output Voltage," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2143-2155, Sept. 2020, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2019.2961853.
- [13] T. Liu, C. Chen, K. Xu, Y. Zhang and Y. Kang, "GaN-Based Megahertz Single-Phase Inverter With a Hybrid TCM Control Method for High Efficiency and High-Power Density," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 6797-6813, June 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.3039386.
- [14] I. Sheikhan, N. Kaminski, S. Voss, W. Scholz and E. Herweg, "Optimisation of the reverse conducting IGBT for zero-voltage switching applications such as induction cookers," *IET Circuits, Devices & Systems*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 176-181, May 2014. doi: 10.1049/iet-cds.2013.0215.
- [15] L. A. Barragan, J. M. Burdío, J. I. Artigas, D. Navarro, J. Acero and D. Puyal, "Efficiency optimization in ZVS series resonant inverters with asymmetrical voltage-cancellation control," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 1036-1044, Sept. 2005. doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2005.854024.
- [16] M. Fernández, X. Perpiñà, M. Vellvehi, O. Aviñó-Salvadó, S. Llorente and X. Jordà, "Power Losses and Current Distribution Studies by Infrared Thermal Imaging in Soft- and Hard-Switched IGBTs Under Resonant Load," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 5221-5237, May 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2019.2942830.
- [17] F. Bonet, O. Aviñó-Salvadó, M. Vellvehi, X. Jordà, P. Godignon and X. Perpiñà, "Carrier Concentration Analysis in 1.2 kV SiC Schottky Diodes Under Current Crowding," in *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 938-941, June 2022, doi: 10.1109/LED.2022.3171112.
- [18] H. Suzuki and M. Ciappa, "TCAD simulation of current filamentation in adjacent IGBT cells under turn-on and turn-off short circuit condition," *Microelectronics Reliability*, vol. 55, no. 9–10, pp. 1976–1980, Aug. 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microrel.2015.06.110>.
- [19] J. Altet, E. Aldrete-Vidrio, D. Mateo, X. Perpiñà, X. Jordà, M. Vellvehi, J. Millán, A. Salhi, S. Grauby, and W. Claeys, "A heterodyne method for the thermal observation of the electrical behavior of high-frequency integrated circuits," *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 19, no. 11, p. 115704, Sep. 2008, doi: 10.1088/0957-0233/19/11/115704.
- [20] J. León, X. Perpiñà, J. Altet, M. Vellvehi, and X. Jordà, "Spatially and frequency-resolved monitoring of intradie capacitive coupling by heterodyne excitation infrared lock-in thermography," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 102, no. 5, p. 054103, Feb. 2013, doi: 10.1063/1.4790299.
- [21] C. Ferrer, O. Aviñó, M. Vellvehi, X. Jordà, X. Perpiñà, "Die-Level Transient Thermal Imaging Based on Fourier Series Reconstruction for Power Industrial Electronics," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 72, pp. 1-11, 2023, Art no. 4508011, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2023.3322477.
- [22] I. Widjaja, A. Kurnia, D. Divan and K. Shenai, "Computer simulation and design optimization of IGBT's in soft-switching converters," in *Proc. Int. Symp. Power Semicon. Dev. ICs (ISPSD)*, Davos, May 1994, pp. 105-109. doi: 10.1109/ISPSD.1994.583664.
- [23] A. Kurnia, H. Cherradi and D. M. Divan, "Impact of IGBT behavior on design optimization of soft switching inverter topologies," *IEEE T. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 280-286, March-April 1995. doi: 10.1109/28.370274.
- [24] J. Villa, J. I. Artigas, J. R. Beltrán, A. D. Vicente and L. A. Barragán, "Analysis of the Acoustic Noise Spectrum of Domestic Induction Heating Systems Controlled by Phase-Accumulator Modulators," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 8, pp. 5929-5938, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2018.2870351.
- [25] M. Mohammadi and M. Ordonez, "Inrush Current Limit or Extreme Startup Response for LLC Converters Using Average Geometric Control," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 777-792, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2017.2666803.
- [26] M. Vellvehi, X. Perpiñà, G. L. Lauro, F. Perillo, and X. Jordà, "Irradiance-based emissivity correction in infrared thermography for electronic applications," *Review of Scientific Instruments* 82, 114901 (2011), doi:10.1063/1.3657154
- [27] O. Breitenstein, W. Warta, M. Langenkamp, "Chapter 2 Physical and Technical Basics," *Lock-in Thermography*, Springer Series in Advanced Microelectronics 10, 2018, pp. 19-62, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-99825-1_2.
- [28] 650 V, 40A IGBT - Field Stop, Trench, FGH40T65SHDF, On Semiconductor®, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.onsemi.com/download/data-sheet/pdf/fg40t65shdf-d.pdf>
- [29] M. Rencz and V. Szekely, "Studies on the nonlinearity effects in dynamic compact model generation of packages," in *IEEE Transactions on Components and Packaging Technologies*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 124-130, March 2004, doi: 10.1109/TCAPT.2004.825750.
- [30] M. Fernández et al., "Solid-State Relay Solutions for Induction Cooking Applications Based on Advanced Power Semiconductor Devices," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 1832-1841, March 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2018.2838093.